

ADVANCEMENT OF INSTRUMENTATION AND SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS FOR GROUNDWATER QUALITY ASSESSMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15269530>

Abstract. *There are many sources of pollution that affect the quality of groundwater, making it unfit for human consumption. The main hydrogeochemical indicators that affect the quality of groundwater are pH, TDS, temperature and water level. The developed device and software combine IoT-based sensors to collect real-time data measuring the main parameters of water quality mentioned above. Wireless communication modules allow continuous data transmission to a centralized platform, which ensures remote access. The data coming from the sensors can be displayed in a tabular format in our web application. The software component, developed using the Node.js framework, provides mechanisms for data visualization, historical analysis and warning for anomalies. The proposed solution improves decision-making, optimizes resource allocation, and improves fault detection, which greatly contributes to more sustainable groundwater monitoring. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the system in real-time monitoring and its ability to analyze groundwater hydrogeochemical parameters using machine learning algorithms.*

Keywords: *groundwater, well, hydrogeochemical parameters, A9G module, IoT, NRF radio module, JSN-SR04T ultrasonic sensor, pH sensor, TDS sensor, temperature sensor, microcontroller, mineralization, web application, battery.*

INTRODUCTION

Due to the increasing anthropogenic impact on water resources, changes in the quality and quantity of water resources, aging of hydraulic structures and melioration systems, the lack of a rational water accounting system, it is necessary to develop a comprehensive system that ensures sustainable development of water resources and benefits the economy of Uzbekistan.

At present, the rational use of groundwater resources is of great importance to meet the needs of the world's population for drinking water. Of the water resources available in the world, 97% is salt water and 3% is fresh water. 68% of the world's fresh water reserves are concentrated in glaciers, while rivers and lakes account for only 2% of fresh water reserves, or 93,000 km³. 30% of drinking water resources are located in the underground hydrosphere. Therefore, the study of the state of the underground hydrosphere and the efficient use of groundwater, the formation of a database and the improvement of methods for mathematical modeling of geofiltration processes are urgent tasks. In developed countries, including the USA, Germany, Canada, Denmark, Japan,

France, and Russia, computer and mathematical modeling methods are widely used to manage phenomena and processes occurring in complex hydrogeological conditions.

Over the years of independence, our republic has taken comprehensive measures to assess and effectively monitor groundwater resources, developed and implemented methods for mathematical modeling of phenomena and processes occurring in complex hydrogeological conditions, and achieved certain results. In this regard, it is necessary to highlight a number of scientific studies aimed at improving the geofiltration processes of regional hydrogeological zones based on the information support of a mathematical model that allows determining the state of the hydrogeological zone and predicting the parameters of the underground hydrosphere [1][2][3].

Nowadays, automated methods for measuring the parameters of the underground hydrological regime have become widespread in the practice of foreign countries. The total mineralization of groundwater is monitored within the framework of a system of regular observations of the parameters of the hydroregime of the aquifer. Automated groundwater monitoring includes systems for monitoring changes in groundwater conditions under the influence of natural and man-made factors, forecasting resources, and using automated methods[4][5][6][7].

The following set of physical, chemical, and biological indicators is used to characterize the hydrogeological properties of groundwater:

- Hydroregime characteristics: water level, groundwater table slope, water volume, etc.
 - Hydrochemical regime characteristics: water mineralization (salinity), salinity, concentration of organic, biogenic, and pollutant substances[8][9].
- Hydrogeological monitoring is necessary to understand and manage groundwater resources, as well as to ensure the quality and availability of water for various purposes. The advent of automated instruments and software solutions has significantly improved the accuracy, efficiency, and reliability of hydrogeochemical measurements. These technologies provide continuous monitoring, real-time data collection, and advanced analysis of critical parameters such as pH, temperature, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, and concentrations of various ions and pollutants.

METHODOLOGY

The research applied the principles of using automated instruments and software to measure hydrogeochemical parameters in hydrogeological monitoring. Development of innovative hardware and software. Automated hydrogeological monitoring instruments typically include sensors, databases, and telemetry systems that work together to collect and transmit data from wells, aquifers, and other groundwater sources. Modern sensors are designed to operate in harsh environmental conditions and provide accurate measurements with minimal human intervention. Data loggers store collected data over a period of time, and telemetry systems transmit data to central databases or cloud platforms for analysis and visualization. Software solutions play a critical role in processing, analyzing, and interpreting hydrogeochemical data. Sophisticated algorithms are used to model groundwater flow, predict pollutant transport, and assess aquifer properties. These software tools make it easier for hydrogeologists to integrate large data sets, enabling them to identify trends, detect anomalies, and make informed decisions about water management [10][11].

There are many methods recommended in various literature for determining water levels and quality; such as capacitance, fiber optic, infrared, vacuum technology, etc. In our proposed method, we conduct measurements using ultrasound and radio waves. In our proposed method,

our device consists of 2 parts. The main part collects this data in its memory for 1 year and then sends it to our integrated central web application when there is a mobile internet connection. The main part of the device is installed at the wellhead and is powered by a solar panel and an LED battery, which guarantees a service life of at least 4 years for this source [12][13].

Based on the information technology support for monitoring in the above observation processes, it is relevant to replace the manual measurement process with automated sensors when collecting observation data at hydrogeological stations of our republic. This process contributes to the efficient management of groundwater resources and the accurate and complete collection of monitoring data[14]15].

The principles of using automated hardware and software in hydrogeological monitoring are based on accuracy, reliability and efficiency. Sensor calibration, regular maintenance and data verification are critical to ensuring the quality of measurements. In addition, the integration of software with automated equipment allows for real-time monitoring and remote access to data, which increases the ability to quickly respond to changing hydrogeochemical conditions. Data Transmission Section. This section is a device that uses the NRF24L01+PA+LNA radio transmitter to transmit data from sensors over long distances (1–5 km) via wireless data exchange protocols. The power supply is the part of the device that provides our microcontrollers and other devices with sufficient electrical current.

Figure 1: The components of our groundwater quality monitoring equipment

There are 1- Arduino Mega 2560 Rev3 microcontroller, 2- DS18B20 water temperature sensor (temperature sensor), 3- pH sensor model, 4- TDS module, detects water quality and other parameters, 5- NRF24L01+PA+LNA radio transmitter and receiver, 6- JSN-SR04T ultrasonic sensor, 7- A9G GSM+GPS module, 8- 300W solar panel kit, high-efficiency all-weather waterproof charger, high output power, 9- 3.5V-5V battery LED. Arduino Mega 2560 Rev3 microcontroller specifications: Microcontroller: ATmega2560 (16MHz clock rate, 8-bit AVR core). Memory 256 KB Flash (program storage), 8 KB SRAM, 4 KB EEPROM. Input and output pins: 54 digital K / CH (15 PWM), 16 analog inputs. For communication, 4 UART (serial), SPI, I2C buses are used. V: 5 V logic, 7-12 V input (via a barrel jack or VIN pin). It is an ideal microcontroller for complex projects that require multiple sensors or communication modules, due to the sufficient number of pins and memory for applications. Features of the DS18B20 water temperature sensor: Digital 1-wire interface.

The temperature range that the sensor can detect is from -55°C to $+125^{\circ}\text{C}$. The sensor has a measurement accuracy of $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ (from -10°C to $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$). Adjustable (9-12 bits). Made of water-resistant stainless steel with a waterproof coating. The power supply consumes an external voltage of 3-5.5 V. It provides reliable and waterproof temperature measurements, which is important for the aquatic environment. Features of the Water Quality pH Sensor: The water pH sensor is a sensor used to determine the pH value of water. Its main function is to measure the ratio of hydrogen ions (H^+) to hydroxyl ions (OH^-) in water molecules to determine whether the water is acidic or alkaline. pH is the ratio of the concentration of hydrogen ions to hydroxyl ions in a water molecule, usually expressed as a pH number, which ranges from 0 to 14, where a lower pH indicates acidity and a higher pH indicates alkalinity. The pH level of food is directly related to the free hydrogen ions in it. Acids present in food release free hydrogen ions; hydrogen ions give acidic foods their characteristic sour taste. Thus, pH can be defined as a measure of free acidity. More precisely, pH is defined as the negative logarithm of the hydrogen ion concentration. The pH range extends from zero to 14. A pH value of 7 is considered neutral because the pH value of pure water is exactly 7. Values below 7 are acidic; Values greater than 7 are considered basic or alkaline.

Accordingly to our well data collection device consists of the following main parts:

1) Sensors - This part of our device helps in measuring various physical quantities of well water. For example: physical quantities such as acidity or alkalinity of water, water temperature, and well depth can be extracted.

2) Power Management - This part of the device prevents our sensors and microcontrollers from being damaged by high voltage and provides sufficient power to all parts of the device.

3) Communication - Usually, electrical appliances located under the well require wireless communication with other devices, so we have used a radio device, which is relatively inexpensive and has a long range. This part of the device serves to transmit information over long distances.

4) The microcontroller is the core part of the device that communicates with all other parts of the device, collects information from the sensors and transmits the information to the device that transmits the information over long distances using NRF radio.

In this part of the device, we have used the following sensors.

PH-4502C - pH Sensor The PH-4502C is a sensor module used to measure the pH of various liquids and soils. This sensor is designed to be integrated with microprocessors such as Arduino, ESP32, Raspberry Pi and provides accurate and reliable results. The PH-4502C pH Sensor is an affordable and reliable sensor used in industries such as agriculture, hydroponics, aquariums and water quality monitoring. It is compatible with Arduino and other platforms, allowing the user to accurately measure the pH of soil and liquids.

It follows that using the NRF radio module, we transmit data from our sensors installed on the surface of the water to our part at the wellhead. Using another NRF radio module at the wellhead, we receive the transmitted data.

This is the ping diagram of the devices in the wellhead section of the device shown in Figure 2 connected to the microcontroller. We installed the receiving part of our NRF radio module, which receives data from the second part of our device, the transmitting part of our NRF radio module, which transmits data collected from our sensors located inside the well, which are in constant contact with groundwater. The structure and operating principle of the device that receives information and transmits it to the user based on the NRF protocol.

Figure 2: The connection diagram of our groundwater quality measurement equipment to the wellhead in Drawio software.

In view of structure of the device that receives information using the NRF protocol and transmits the received data to the user consists of the following main parts:

1) Wireless communication part (Communication) - this part allows our microcontroller to receive information from our device located in the well and deliver it to the desired user. Our device uses radio frequencies to receive information and SMS messages to deliver information to the user.

2) The microcontroller is the core part of our device, it communicates with other devices, receives data from other microcontrollers via NRF and delivers it to the user via SMS. The advantage of the device is that it can be connected to web applications without any additional elements. In the next step, we will send the data received from the receiving part of our radio module to our web application (get) using the A9G GSM module. A9G is a multifunctional wireless communication module that includes GSM / GPRS and GPS functions, developed by Ai-Thinker. This module allows you to make calls, send SMS messages, connect to the Internet, determine location using GPS and perform many other wireless communication operations. The A9G module is widely used in IoT (Internet of Things) projects, automated devices, GPS tracking systems and remote control systems. To power our device from an alternative energy source, we use a 300V solar panel kit, which is a highly efficient, waterproof, weatherproof, high output charger with a 3.5V-5V battery LED indicator.

For the central control part of the device, I used the Arduino Uno microcontroller. Arduino Uno is an easy-to-use open-source microcontroller platform used in electronic devices, IoT, automation, and many other projects. It is based on the Atmel ATmega328P chip and features digital and analog I/O, USB interface, power ports, and other features. Arduino Uno is one of the most popular entry-level platforms for students, engineers, and programmers. In the Power Management section, we used Power Management. Since our device combines two wireless communication modules, and these communication devices consume more than 2 amps of current in the active state, I paid special attention to choosing the right power source and used rechargeable lithium batteries. But since the voltage generated by these lithium batteries is high, I used the LM2596 regulator to generate the required voltage for my Arduino microcontroller.

Figure 3: Drawing of the device in the power supply management section.

In addition, to make the device more autonomous and eco-friendly, I have added solar panels to my project. Thanks to these panels, the lithium batteries are constantly charged and our device can work continuously. At the same time, using solar energy reduces the dependence on the power grid and allows our device to work more efficiently.

The second part of the device houses several components, including sensors, a communication module, and a power management system. Below is a breakdown of the components and their connections:

Main components and their connections: Microcontroller (Arduino Mega 2560). The Arduino Mega 2560 serves as the main control unit that processes the input data from the sensors and transmits the data through the communication module. Since our device is underground, we needed to choose the right wireless communication medium so that it can freely exchange information with other devices. The pH sensor module is connected to the following pins of Arduino Mega 2560: VCC → VCC (5V), GND → GND, PO (analog output) → A0 (analog input). The DS18B20 temperature sensor (water temperature) is connected to the pins VCC → 5V, GND → GND, DQ (data) → GPIO7. The TDS (Total Dissolved Solids) sensor is connected to VCC → 5V, GND → GND, A (analog output) → A1 (analog input) pins.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of part of our groundwater quality measurement equipment equipped with borehole sensors in Drawio.

Figure 4 shows the wiring diagram of the electronic system using Arduino Mega 2560 as the central microcontroller. Several components are connected, including sensors, communication module and power management system. The ultrasonic sensor (water level measurement) is

connected to the pins VCC → 5V, GND → GND, Trig → D6, Echo → D7. I used the NRF24L01+PA+LNA radio transmitter and receiver to transmit data from the sensors to the radio model at the wellhead. For this, we decided to use the nRF24L01 module and the NRF radio protocol. The 433 MHz radio module transmits the processed data to the remote receiver for real-time monitoring. Power management system. The battery is connected to a step-down DC-DC converter, the battery output is 10V → DC-DC, the converter input is connected to the converter output → Arduino VCC to 5V, GND → GND pins. The power supply system ensures uninterrupted operation using the battery and voltage regulator to provide stable power. Our pH sensor has the following connection scheme to the microcontroller:

- 1) VCC → 5V (PH-4502C ---> Arduino mega)
- 2) GND → GND (PH-4502C ---> Arduino mega)
- 3) PO → A0 (PH-4502C ---> Arduino mega) (pH value measurement output)

The next main sensor we used in our device is TDS Board V1.2, which detects the temperature and salinity of the water. This electronic device includes a DS18B20 temperature sensor and a TDS salinity sensor. TDS Board V1.2 is a module used to measure the total dissolved solids (TDS) in water based on electrical conductivity (EC). This sensor is designed for use in aquariums, hydroponics, water quality control and other purposes.

Figure 5: General view of our device used for groundwater monitoring: a) part of the main module at the wellhead, b) part equipped with sensors located on the water surface.

RESEARCH RESULTS

I developed a web application that displays groundwater readings in a tabular format using Node.js. This application can be connected to your Django web application or to a separate standalone server. Backend: Node.js + Express.js - API creation. Use Sequelize or Mongoose as an ORM in the database section. RESTful API - retrieving and processing sensor data. Frontend: React.js or Vue.js - table visualization. Recharts or Chart.js - reading groundwater data from sensors and plotting graphs. Filtering and searching functionality when outputting in tabular form. Data retrieval via JSON API. Visualization was achieved by creating graphs and charts. The interface of our web application looks like this, and you can change it as you wish. This does not require any programming skills from the user. The difference of this central device is that it

transmits all the collected information to our web application via WiFi wireless data exchange protocols.

Figure 6: Interface of the web application for creating groundwater indicators

These 6 images show the interface of the web application created using Node.js. Below I will provide some information about this application: The main functions of the application. Monitoring system: The application displays data from sensors or devices in a certain area in real time. Displaying sensor data:

- Temperature (Temperature)
- Water level (Water level)
- Salinity level TDS
- pH value

On the right side of our web application, there is information about the device (name, status, operator number, location, etc.).

Table 1. Results obtained from measuring the water level using an automatic measuring device

No	Set level in laboratory conditions, m	Results obtained from the device, m	Error, m
	1	0,998	0,001
	2	1,992	0,006
	5	4,991	0,008
	7	6,990	0,01
	10	9,987	0,012

Table 2. Results obtained when measuring water temperature

No	Specified temperature in laboratory conditions, °C	Results obtained from the device, °C	Error, °C
1	1	1	0
2	10	9,998	0,001
3	20	20,011	- 0,001
4	25	25,001	- 0,001
5	30	29,989	0,001

In laboratory studies, the measurement error of the level for 5 different volumes of water

was 0–0.012 m, temperature 0–0.001 °C, electrical conductivity 0.88–3.04%. Thus, based on the results of comparative studies, it was established that the measurement accuracy of the data of the studied device is higher than that of existing automated measuring devices.

Stationary hydrogeological observations aimed at studying the elements that make up the groundwater regime and its balance allow us to provide a qualitative and quantitative characteristic of the processes of groundwater formation, identify the main patterns of spatio-temporal changes in their quantity, quality and properties, justify the development, development and protection of the most rational measures for the use of groundwater, the composition of projects to combat their harmful effects, and methods for managing their monitoring regime.

CONCLUSION

Measuring the hydrogeochemical parameters of groundwater is one of the important areas of modern environmental monitoring. Changes in water quality are associated with human activities, natural geochemical processes and the ecological environment, and such monitoring requires effective technologies and accurate measuring equipment.

The purpose of this study is to develop a device and a corresponding web-based software application that measures groundwater hydrogeochemical parameters, including pH, TDS, temperature and level. This system is characterized by the ability to perform real-time measurements, process data and analyze them.

The research results show that the developed device is faster and more convenient to use than traditional laboratory methods. The software performs the functions of visualization, analysis and storage of collected data. This will automate environmental monitoring and hydrogeological studies, as well as effectively control the quality of groundwater resources.

In the future, it is planned to further develop the system, integrate Internet of Things technologies and improve monitoring efficiency by expanding the capabilities of artificial intelligence-based analysis. This will help strengthen scientific and practical approaches to the rational use and protection of water resources.

The system is developed on the basis of scientific and methodological principles and has the ability to collect, analyze and evaluate data in real time. As a result of automation of groundwater quality monitoring, continuous measurements were carried out in observation wells, which significantly increased the efficiency of hydrogeological studies.

The results of the study provided the following benefits: Continuous observation and monitoring - the dynamics of the water level are accurately measured in real time, and the data is transmitted to the central system. Efficiency of groundwater resource management - the process of monitoring groundwater quality indicators is significantly simplified using an automated system. The possibility of analyzing hydrogeological processes - trends in changes in groundwater quality indicators was revealed, and a strategy for the use of water resources was formed.

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